

THE IMPORTANCE OF CRITICAL READING IN EAP

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Abstract: *It is undeniable that critical reading is crucial in academic area. To be a critical reader requires to acquire certain skills and strategies from an academic student. In order to be a good reader one should pass certain ways. Critical reading is considered to be a hot topic among scholars. It has been taught by prominent scholars like Krashen, Hudson, Davies, Manzo, Grabel, Gordon, Rosenshell and Rowsel and Walsh. This article highlights on these scholars' views about critical reading, strategies, problems, activities and results of surveys.*

Key words: *critical, strategy, academic, reading, skills.*

Introduction According to Hudson (2007), Critical reading skill is one of the most important part of reading skill. Not only it enables readers to analyze, synthesize and evaluate what is being read but also it helps students to be a critical thinkers. Marshall, Rowland and Kurland (1998) agree with this view. «Critical reading requires critical thinking" While Krashen (1995) states Critical skill is a skill which we apply in our both academic and social lives. Proctor and Dutta (1995) Gives a definition to reading skill. Initially, skill is obtained through practice or training. They are not natural ability but learned. Second, skill is improved when a reader exposed some environment. Third, reading can be improved when reading behavior is well organized. Eventually, Cognitive demands are declined when the critical reading skill is acquired. Moreover, Tierney and Pearson, (1994) claims that reading is considered to be active process called cognitive. Davies (1995) argues that reading can be not only active but also passive as well. Manzo (1988) defines that Reading is the act of reading the lines, between lines and beyond lines while Grabe (1988) states that reading is a dialogue between the reader and text.

REASONS AND PROBLEMS FOR CRITICAL READING

Wallace (2003) states that There are 3 driving forces behind for reading. 1. We read to survive 2. We read to learn 3. we read for pleasure. According to his view, we should identify the needs of readers, find an answer why they are reading, Then we can make a reading process more enjoyable. Heidi Byrnes believes that the reason for reading is to understand the text. Wallace (2003) one of the problems with teachers is they do not help students to construct meaning from context. Another issue related to reading in schools is "genre". Wigfield and Guthrie state that the reason why most

learners can not improve their critical reading skills is lack of motivation. And it divided motivation into 3 (competence, reading efficacy and achievement values)

CRITICAL READING SKILLS, STRATEGIES AND ACTIVITIES

Hudson (2007) divides reading skills into 4.

1. Word attack skills - where students are able to understand single units such as phonemes , syllables, and words. 2. Comprehension skills - students are able to get the meaning from context.3. Fluency skills- Students are able to improve their abilities including word recognition, rapid reading and possessing an extensive vocabulary. 4. critical reading skill. - students are capable of analyzing in detail what they read.

Rosenshine (1980) believes that there are 3 reading categories (locating detail, simple inferential skill and complex inferential skill and reading includes seven sub-skills. whereas Gordon (1982) argues that There are 3 subskills , reading skills development, reading comprehension, and reading research. Whereas Knott's(2005) divided it into 6. According to Richards, Platt and Webster(1985) , strategy is a set of processes utilized in learning thinking , which creates a way of attaining a goal. and they can be both conscious and unconscious. Whereas Paris, Wasik, and Turner state Skill is natural while strategy is consciously acquired that Strategies are mor proficient and remarkably advanced when they are employed in automatic way as skills. Moreover, They divide strategies into 3

1.pre-reading strategies 2. while-reading strategies 3. post-reading strategies as well as 11 elements. Rumelhat (1977) and Stanovich(1980) states In critical reading, Top-down and bottom-up models are equally important to skilled reading whilst Urquhart and Weir (1980) consider that These two strategies demonstrate different balance in intensive reading or reading.

Metacognitive skills. John Flavell states that metacognitive strategy are produced to control cognitive process while pierce(2004) concludes that it is "thinking about thinking" Wallace (2003) applies 3 types of activities into critical reading , pre-reading , while-reading and post-reading activities. Similarly Kress(1987) also gave the same view on that topic. Borg and Gall(2003) concludes that critical learning models includes 2 types of activities structured and feasible activities. While Nutall(1996) argues that Authentic materials based on real-life situations should be used to improve students' critical reading. He also divided activities into 3 (pre, while and post). Rowsel and Walsh (2011) states that multimodal tasks have positive impact on students' critical reading abilities. They conducted a research a research on two groups, one in control group and the other in experimental group. In the first group, Students are taught reading with multitasks while in the second group lessons were conducted with only one task. The students in experimental group was more successful. Another similar study has been conducted on this topic by Miss SaviakaVarapon (2019) but The content was different. This professor first did 2 tests pre and post tests. They reported that multimodeltasks affect positively to students'

critical reading skills and enhance at the same time. The term “multiliteracies” refers to multiple literacies that are stretched beyond the constraints of written and spoken language. The fact that people can incorporate various features like audios, videos, pictures, and animations to communicate a message to the world or among individuals opens up new possibilities for communication (Jewitt, 2008). Based on this view, literacy is no longer a set of linguistic skills one must master, so it needs to be pluralized into literacies. In line with Jewitt (2008), while The New London Group suggested that the pedagogy of multiliteracies matched with the twin goals of literacy education. The first goal is to expose students to multimodality and the second is to equip the students with the necessary tools for active and critical engagement with these new forms of meaning making resources. The key principle of the multiliteracies pedagogy is to ensure that active participation and intellectual engagement of students are scaffolded through a range of tasks such as thinking, discussing, problem-solving, synthesizing, theorizing, or drawing conclusions (Haren, 2010).

Conclusion

All in all, critical reading plays a vital role in reading effectively. Different scholars gave different definitions to it, as it was stated above and there are some reasons and problems behind it in terms of students' personality and teachers' instructions as well. We have critical reading skills, strategies and some suggested type of activities by some scholars. And some of them conducted researches on critical reading especially, on the effects of multitasking on improving learners' critical reading. Research question can be as following: how can students' critical reading skills be improved? What is the importance of critical reading in an academic sphere?

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